

MORPHOLOGICAL STUDY OF pCBT AND ITS CARBON FIBER-REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

The crystalline morphologies and behavior of in-situ polymerized CBT and its carbon fiber reinforced composites were investigated. The crystalline morphologies of in-situ polymerized CBT changed with the crystallization temperature. Axialite was found at T_c below 195°C whereas mixed type spherulite co-exist with axialite occurred at T_c = 198~203°C and a roughly spherical shape crystalline without defined borders was revealed at 205~213°C. The axialite crystallized at 195°C with higher crystal growth rate may be the root cause of the brittleness of in-situ polymerized pCBT.

Keywords: cyclic butylene terephthalate (CBT), morphology, in-situ polymerization, regime transition, Axialite

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Keywords: cyclic butylene terephthalate (CBT), morphology, crystallization during polymerization, Axialite

INTRODUCTION

The developed macrocyclic butylene terephthalate (CBT) oligomer has been successfully prepared by ring/chain equilibration (cyclo-depolymerization) of the waste poly butylene terephthalate in dilute solution. CBT is then readily polymerized to linear high molecular weight poly(butylene terephthalate (pCBT) in the presence of tin or titanium catalysts within few minutes (3-5 min at 190°C). Recent interests in CBT are not only for its recycling concept to manage the growing waste polymer problem and it also provides promising characters to stimulate the development of thermoplastic composites. CBT has some important advantages for thermoplastic composites processing: water like low viscosity (36mPa.s at 190°C), the capability of rapid polymerization into polybutylene terephthalate (pCBT), no low-molecular weight byproducts evolution and the ability to be processed like thermoset resins such as RTM [1].

CBT polymerization can be performed below and above the melting temperature of the resulting pCBT (~225°C). DSC studies on the polymerization of CBT have been published and information on the crystallization and melting behavior of the resulting pCBT is also available [2]. Tripathy et al. [3] have studied the polymerization of CBT using different catalysts and have found that the selected catalyst strongly influence the polymer conversion and the time required for polymerization. Fast catalyst such as stannoxane (XB2) was found to complete CBT polymerization within 2-3 min at 190°C,

whereas slow catalyst as in the tetrakis-(2-ethylhexyl) titanate (OGTR) system consumes more than 15 min to complete the polymerization. The polymerization of CBT is regarded as an athermal process because it is an entropically driven ring-expansion polymerization. This is important as the high Mw of the resulting pCBT because the system will not thermally degrade thick sections or significantly raise mold temperature. Only small amount of heat is generated during the crystallization process. It is therefore hard to distinguish the polymerization and crystallization process by using thermograph only. Hakme et al. [4] have studied the polymerization and crystallization kinetics of CBT by dielectric sensing. When the process temperature above 220°C, only the CBT polymerization occurs. At process temperature above 200°C, polymerization first following by crystallization, whereas a simultaneous polymerization and crystallization occurs at the temperature below 200°C. This simultaneous process can affect crystal morphology and hence the final properties of the polymer.

The crystal structure of pCBT is asserted to be the same as the engineering plastic, poly(butylene terephthalate) (PBT). PBT has a triclinic unit cell for both known polymorphs, α being the predominant polymorph, whereas the β polymorph is only observed in drawn and spun fiber. In addition, it was reported for PBT that three different types of spherulites are formed in thin films under static condition, depending on the crystallization conditions. Lorenzo and Righetti [5] concluded the morphologies of PBT as: an unusual type spherulite was found at T_c below 194°C, and then changes to usual-mixed type at $T_c = 204^\circ\text{C}$, whereas at 214°C the spherulitic pattern was lost or not well defined. Several studies have also conducted on crystallization kinetics of PBT. Data available in the literature mainly concern analysis of the bulk crystallization rate of PBT, measured both in isothermal and non-isothermal conditions, and only limited data exist on analysis of growth rate (G) of PBT spherulites [6]. It is owing to the difficulties in the determination of G arising from the very high nucleation density of PBT. Lorenzo and Righetti [5] studied the crystallization of PBT and concluded a II-III regime transition occurs at 211°C, accompanied by a change in crystal morphology.

Parton et al., [7] studied the mechanical properties of pCBT and found isothermal polymerized and crystallized pCBT leads to big perfect crystals which induce brittleness. It is therefore of paramount important to understand and control the crystallization of the in-situ polymerized CBT. However, only MacKnight [3] and Parton [8] have used SALS to study the morphology of melt crystallized pCBT. A four-leaf-clover-type pattern was clearly observed in the Hv mode for isothermal temperature above 195°C. When the crystallization temperature is lower to 190°C, the “unusual” type spherulite was observed. Interestingly, the morphology of pCBT and its spherulite growth have not been yet reported.

These issues were therefore the objective of this paper. The crystalline behavior and morphologies of in-situ polymerized CBT and its carbon fiber reinforced composites were investigated by thermal difference scanning analyzer (DSC) and polarized light microscope (PLM). Spherulite growth rate results were analyzed according to the Hoffman and Lauritzen theory to give.

EXPERIMENT

Materials.

CBT pellets (Grade:160) purchased from Cyclics (Schenectady, NY; www.cyclics.com) was used throughout this study. This CBT is produced by using XB3 catalyst with average molecular weight $M_w = (220)_n$ ($n=2-7$) for the purposes of engineering plastic and composite applications. CBT was dried in a vacuum oven for overnight at 85°C and kept in a desiccator until further use.

Tests

The crystallization and melting behavior of pCBT were examined by thermal difference scanning analyzer (TA-Du pont DSC Q10 series) under isothermal conditions. For isothermal crystallization kinetics study, specimens were heated to the desired crystallization temperature, T_c at the heating rate of 120°C/min, held for 3 folds of the time at crystallization peak to allow completing the polymerization. The crystallization temperature is between 190~215°C. Then, the specimens were cooling to room temperature. The resulting crystallized specimens were then heating to 265°C at the rate of 20°C/min for the melting behavior and melt temperature determination.

Morphologies and spherulite growth rates (G) of pCBT were determined by polarized light microscope equipped with a Linkam TMHS 600 hot stage. A small piece of CBT was squeezed between two microscope slides, then inserted in the hot stage. Dry nitrogen was used as purge gas in the hot stage during all measurements and thermal treatments. The thermal treatment conditions follow the conditions described above for DSC crystallization kinetics study. The radius of a growing spherulite (r) as measured as a function of time (t) by taking photomicrographs at appropriate time intervals. From the slope of the lines obtained by plotting r against t , G was derived for the T_c range 190-215°C. A quartz plate was used to determine the sign of the birefringence of the pCBT spherulites.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Morphology of pCBT and its Carbon Fiber-reinforced Composites

Figure 1 shows the spherulite morphology of pCBT thin films in-situ polymerized and crystallized at temperatures between 190~215°C. Three different types of pCBT morphology were identified as axialite at polymerization/crystallization temperature (T_c) below 195 °C (Figure 1a), and mixed type spherulite co-exist with axialite at $T_c = 198\sim 203^\circ\text{C}$ (Figure 1b) and crystalline with a roughly spherical shape and less defined borders at 205~213°C (Figure 1c). These PLM morphologies explain the SALS results [5] that a ‘unusual type’ spherulites crystallized at low temperature (below 195 °C) but a ‘usual type’ is observed at higher crystallization temperature (above 195 °C). The “axialite” like morphology is the first time reported which crystallized along with in-situ polymerization and never seen in PBT. Its growth sequences are illustrated with Figure 2. Rod like crystal appears and grows along the axial direction firstly. Rod thickening is also observed with slower growth rate. In the later growth stage, sheaf-like (axialite) crystal with two thicker ends is revealed. The resulting morphology can be attributed to the rate competition between the polymerization and crystallization. When the rate of crystallization is lower than that of polymerization, mixed type spherulite morphology is observed as shown in Figure 1b. On the contrary, axialite morphology is obtained. This

observation confirmed the statement of Wunderlich [9], simultaneous polymerization and crystallization can lead to a very different crystal morphology ranging from a fully extended chain conformation to a folded chain conformation. The slower polymerization rate indicates an insufficient pCBT chain supply for crystallization and most of space is occupied with CBT oligomer. The extended rod growth suggests the pCBT chain polymerized mostly in front of the crystallized laminate growth frontage. The mixed type spherulite co-exist with axialite morphologies revealed the rates of polymerization and crystallization are almost the same. When T_c between 195~200°C, axialite is the dominative crystal. Axialite initiates and grows ahead of the mixed type spherulite. On the Contrary, When T_c between 200~205°C, axialite is the dominative crystal. Axialite initiates and grows ahead of the mixed type spherulite. When T_c above 203°C, the polymerization rate is much higher than the crystallization rate. The morphology in Figure 1c has also been found in PBT at T_c above 214°C [5]. Interestingly, no clear spherulite/axialite boundary has been found in the in-situ polymerized/crystallized pCBT crystalline. Please note that the brittleness of pCBT crystallized at 195°C have been attributed to the perfection of pCBT crystals [7]. That is, the axialite crystallized in regime III may be the root cause of the brittleness.

Figure 3 shows the PLM images for pCBT samples with carbon fiber and crystallized for the three different morphologies. The nucleation effectiveness of the carbon fiber is revealed. The crystalline morphology at the vicinity of the carbon fiber surfaces has no influence when $T_c = 195^\circ\text{C}$ where axialite morphology was shown. At higher T_c , the carbon fiber increased the density of spherulites and decreased the size of crystallites acting as crystallization nucleation sites without exhibiting transcrystallites at the vicinity of the carbon fiber surfaces.

Regime Transition Analysis of pCBT

Two kinds of growth rate, axialite and spherulite as revealed previous, of pCBT measured in the range between 195~213°C are reported in Figure 4. As expected, at low undercooling the rate of growth decreases with increasing T_c . The growth rate of axialite is higher than that of spherulite. The experimental data of Figure 4 were analyzed using the Hoffman and Lauritzen equation [10]:

$$\ln G = \ln G_0 - \frac{U^*}{R(T_c - T_\infty)} - \frac{K_g}{T_c \Delta T f} \quad (1)$$

where G_0 is a pre-exponential term; R is the universal gas constant; U^* is the energy required for the transport of the macromolecules in the melt; T_c is the crystallization temperature; T_∞ is the temperature where all the motions associated with the viscous flow stop, being defined as $T_\infty = T_g - 56.1$, where T_g is the glass transition temperature; ΔT is the undercooling ($\Delta T = T_m^0 - T_c$), where T_m^0 is the equilibrium melting temperature); f is a corrective factor that takes into account the variation of the equilibrium melting enthalpy with temperature, define as $f = 2 T_c / (T_c + T_m^0)$; K_g is the nucleation constant, is a term connected with the energy needed for the formation of nuclei of critical size.

In order to apply Equation 1, precise values of T_g and T_m^0 are needed. However, only T_g has been limited reported but T_m^0 has not yet been reported. The T_g was determined by quenched pCBT sample and found a glass transition peak at 43°C. The resulting T_g is

reasonable and confirms the determined T_g value (40~43°C) of pCBT by Mohd Ishak et al. [11].

The Hoffman-Weeks procedure was used to determine the equilibrium melting temperature of pCBT. Figure 5 presents DSC thermograms obtained at a heating rate of 20°C/min for specimens that were isothermally treated for in-situ polymerized and crystallized at temperatures between 190~215°C. A single melting peak is observed and the peak temperature shifts to higher temperature as T_c increase. This trend indicates thicker crystalline lamellae develop as T_c increase. As shown in Figure 6, the melting temperatures (T_m) are plotted versus T_c values. According to the Hoffman-Weeks method, the experimental data are extrapolated to the intersection with the $T_c = T_m$ line. The temperature of intersection is T_m^0 , which yields a value of 238 °C.

The regime analysis based on Equation 1 is used to treat the continuous growth rate data, as shown in Figure 7. Whereas, it was determined by using the following values: $U^*=4500$ cal/mol, $T_g = 43^\circ\text{C}$, $T_m^0 = 238^\circ\text{C}$. This analysis suggested two transitions: regime II-III transition at 199°C and special transition correspond to the nucleation of axialite and mixed type spherulite at 205 °C. That is, three nucleation transition were determined for growth rate data at $T_c < 199^\circ\text{C}$ (axialite nucleation), T_c range from 199 to 205°C (mix type spherulite, regime II) and $T_c > 205^\circ\text{C}$ (pCBT spherulite, regime I). Comparing to the II-III transition temperature at 211 °C for PBT [5], there are 13°C lower. However, for the axialite and spherulite morphologic transition in pCBT, it is never reported in PBT.

Isothermal crystallization kinetics of pCBT

Figure 8 shows the DSC thermograms for pCBT specimens isothermally crystallization at various temperatures. It is important to note that double crystallization peaks were found at T_c between 198~203°C. The double crystallization peaks are thus well linked to the mixed type spherulite coexisted with axialite morphologies. According to results of the morphological study, the first crystallization peak is related to the axialite growth whereas the second crystallization peak is associated with the mixed type spherulite growth. Therefore the result confirms the morphological studies and the regime analysis that axialite crystallized in axialite nucleation regime is the dominative crystal at T_c between 195~200°C whereas mixed type spherulite growth in regime II is the dominative crystal at T_c between 200~205°C.

From the results in Figure 8, the crystallization kinetics of polymers under isothermal conditions can then be analyzed according to the known Avrami equation [12]. The basic isothermal Avrami expression provides,

$$X_t = 1 - \exp(-kt^n) \quad (2)$$

The crystallinity can be calculated from Figure 8, and a plot of as the crystallinity a function of temperature is shown in Figure 9.

The double logarithmic transformation, used to obtain the Avrami plot, yields:

$$\ln[-\ln(1 - X_t)] = n \ln t + t \ln k \quad (3)$$

where X_t is the relative crystallinity at different crystallization times, n is a constant depending on the mechanism of nucleation and form of crystal growth, and k is the crystallization rate constant related to nucleation and growth parameters.

According to equation (3), if the crystallization kinetics of a semicrystalline polymer

follow Avrami crystallization kinetics, a plot of $\ln[-\ln(1-X_t)]$ as a function of $\ln(t)$ should be linear, with slope n . When an Avrami plot was constructed from the isothermal data, as shown in Figure 10, the Avrami crystallization kinetics parameters n and k value were determined and summarized in Table 1. When T_c below 200°C which Axialite morphology was found and was attributed to simultaneous polymerization and crystallization, the Avrami constant n is around 2.33-2.75 except $T_c = 195^\circ\text{C}$. This n value suggests a 2-D Axialite and 3-D spherulite coexisted with heterogeneous nucleation mechanism. In contrast, mixed type spherulite and a roughly spherical shape crystalline at $200\sim 213^\circ\text{C}$ with mechanism of polymerization first following by crystallization have n values around 3.44-4.75, indicate a 3-D spherulite in homogenous nucleation mechanism.

CONCLUSION

In this paper, the crystalline morphologies and behavior of in-situ polymerized CBT were investigated by thermal difference scanning analyzer (DSC) and polarized light microscope (PLM). Spherulite growth rate results were analyzed according to the Hoffman and Lauritzen theory. In particular, the following conclusions have been reached:

- 1). The crystalline morphologies of in-situ polymerized CBT changed with the crystallization temperature. Axialite was found at T_c below 195°C whereas mixed type spherulite co-exist with axialite occurred at $T_c = 198\sim 203^\circ\text{C}$ and a roughly spherical shape crystalline without defined borders was revealed at $205\sim 213^\circ\text{C}$.
- 2). Mixed type spherulite co-exist with axialite morphologies are confirmed with the double crystallization peaks at $T_c = 198\sim 203^\circ\text{C}$. The first crystallization peak is related to the axialite growth with higher growth rate whereas the second crystallization peak is associated with the mixed type spherulite growth.
- 3). The axialite crystallized at 195°C with higher crystal growth rate may be the root cause of the brittleness of in-situ polymerized pCBT.

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Figure 1. Three morphologies of pCBT crystal. (a) $T_c=195\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, crystalline growing (b) $T_c=195\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, final morphology (c) $T_c=200\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, crystalline growing (d) $T_c=200\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, final morphology (e) $T_c=210\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, crystalline growing (f) $T_c=210\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, final morphology.

Figure 2. The growth sequences of axialite morphology in pCBT

Figure 3. Morphology of pCBT/Carbon composites. (a) $T_c=195\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, (b) $T_c=200\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, (c) $T_c=210\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$

Figure 4. Growth rates of axialite and spherulite of pCBT measured in the range between 195~213°C

Figure5. DSC thermograms obtained at a heating rate of 20°C/min for specimens that were isothermally treated for in-situ polymerized and crystallized at temperatures between 190~215°C

Figure 6. The Hoffman-Weeks plot by plotting the melting temperatures (T_m) versus T_c values.

Figure 7. Regime analysis of spherulite growth rate data of pCBT

Figure 8. DSC thermograms show specimens that were isothermally treated for in-situ polymerized and crystallized at temperatures between 195~210°C

Figure 9. Development of relative crystallinity with time for isothermal crystallization at temperatures between 195~210°C

Figure 10. Avrami plots for the isothermal crystallization of pCBT at temperatures between 195~210°C

Table 1. Parameters of isothermal crystallization from the Avrami equation

$T_p(^{\circ}\text{C})$	n	$\ln K$	$t_{1/2}(\text{min})$	$T_p(^{\circ}\text{C})$	n	$\ln K$	$t_{1/2}(\text{min})$
195	3.35	-10.43	20.21	203	3.44	-11.24	23.66
198	2.48	-7.60	18.49	205	4.57	-17.06	38.60
200	2.75	-8.85	21.83	210	4.72	-20.27	67.85